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MARinE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management

D7.3 Joint Strategy and Dissemination Plan of Networking Actions

30/12/2021

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Executive Summary

The present document refers to a Joint Strategy and Dissemination Plan of Networking Actions regarding Marine Litter (ML) mitigation, removal and recycling initiatives worldwide.

The document is foreseen as a deliverable of Task 7.3 of the Work Package 7- Coordination and Integration of blue technology for plastic strategy-oriented efforts - of the EU funded MAELSTROM project.

With both numbers and complexity of ML related initiatives increasing, effective coordination and networking among players is more than ever a key aspect to optimize resources, reduce the risk of repetition and maximize impact of mitigation removal and recycling initiatives and technologies. The present strategy aims at contributing to this ambitious mission by directly collecting the perspectives of ML practitioners and stakeholders on current gaps and opportunities of synergies in the field. It furthermore aims at identifying and proposing effective approaches for multi-level stakeholder engagement, hopefully leading to improved policies and actions regarding marine litter reduction, identification, removal and recycling.

The analysis work was divided into three clusters:

- Research on ML and development of blue technologies for ML removal and prevention
- Societal behavioural change and citizen science to reduce ML and support circular/blue economy
- International cooperation and capacity building for ML removal and mitigation actions

The present document represents the first step of MAELSTROM's Joint Strategy and Plan for Networking Actions on marine litter. It is based on the first year of MAELSTROM's stakeholders' engagement activities and thus, it represents a scoping phase that will guide Maelstrom's work during the project and will contribute to other deliverables foreseen by the end of 2024.

Further stakeholder engagement activities such as specific webinars, forum discussions and demonstrative events are expected to provide additional information which will be crucial for a successful Joint Strategy. Such activities will moreover provide the means to map the Best Practices for Marine Litter removal and valorisation (deliverable D 7.2), expected to happen on month 40 and which should be seen as part of the present Strategy.

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1. Introduction to the MAELSTROM project

MAELSTROM is a project funded under the Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. MAELSTROM strives to provide answers and diversified solutions to the complex issues regarding the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter legacy.

MAELSTROM contemplates the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal in different European coastal ecosystems, compounded with full-fledged circular economy and societal oriented solutions. In particular, the project (i) outlines a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas; (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second generation fuel, to identify, remove and sort marine litter; (iii) evaluates over time the effectiveness of marine litter removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems; (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected marine litter into valuable raw materials for future marketisation; (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of the MAELSTROM solutions while providing a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products; (vi) raises social awareness about the marine litter issue and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities; (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximize innovation uptake for marine litter removal within and outside the EU.

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2. MAELSTROM Consortium

The MAELSTROM project consortium consists of the following members:

Table 1- Partner's list and abbreviations

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3. Aim of the Joint Strategy and Dissemination Plan of Networking Actions

The present document refers to a **Joint Strategy and Dissemination Plan of Networking Actions** regarding Marine Litter (ML) mitigation initiatives in the European space. The document is foreseen as a deliverable of Task 7.3 of the Work Package 7 - *Coordination and Integration of blue technology for plastic strategy-oriented efforts* - of the EU funded MAELSTROM project.

MAELSTROM, **MA**rinE Litter **Su**sTainable **Re**mOval and **M**anagement, is a HORIZON 2020 project designed to develop and test sustainable technological solutions for the removal, treatment and recycling of marine litter following a circular economy approach which includes the marketization of regenerated and recycled materials. Among other activities, the project will implement an underwater cable robot in the Venice Lagoon (Italy) and a Bubble Barrier in the Porto Region (Portugal). MAELSTROM is supported by 14 partners from 8 European Countries, including research centres in the fields of marine life, biology, sustainable energy, artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics. Other partners include private multinational /national recycling companies with certified industrial plants, a market consultancy company, a micro-enterprise and a marine litter/plastic orientated NGO.

As the continuous growth in the amount of solid waste thrown away and the slow rate of degradation of most items is leading to a gradual increase of marine litter on ecosystems (UNEP, 2018) also innovative mitigation efforts have been on the rise through political, scientific, technological and civil society initiatives and experiments. According to the Marine Strategy Framework Directive Technical Group¹, within a total of 133 marine-related funded projects in the last decade, 70 projects focused on monitoring and assessment, 27 on prevention and mitigation while 36 projects covered both aspects².

With both numbers and complexity of ML related initiatives increasing, effective coordination and networking among players is more than ever a key aspect to optimize resources, reduce the risk of repetition and maximize impact of mitigation removal and recycling initiatives and technologies.

The present strategy aims at contributing to this ambitious mission by directly collecting the perspectives of ML practitioners and stakeholders on current gaps and opportunities in the field. It furthermore aims at identifying and proposing effective approaches for multi-level stakeholder engagement, hopefully leading to improved policies and actions regarding marine litter reduction, identification, removal and recycling.

¹ https://mcc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/main/dev.py?N=41&O=434&titre_chap=TG

² List of research projects prepared for the MSFD Technical Group on Marine Litter. Current version 20.10.2021. Contributors: TG ML, George Hanke JRC, Anna Addamo JRC, Thomais Vlachogianni MIO-ECSDE, Luis F. Ruiz-Orejón JRC from Maelstrom webinar's presentation of T. Vlachogianni

The analysis work was divided into three clusters:

- Research on ML and development of blue technologies for ML removal and prevention
- Societal behavioural change and citizen science to reduce ML and support circular/blue economy
- International cooperation and capacity building for ML removal and mitigation actions

Practitioners and stakeholders contributing to this strategy were engaged following a participatory approach based on two communication channels: i) a ML dedicated **forum** hosted on the MAELSTROM website; ii) a **webinar** on “Inspiring Science and Society to tackle Marine Litter”, organized by the MAELSTROM partners as a Satellite activity of the United Nations Ocean Decade Laboratory under the call “A Clean Ocean”.

The present document represents the first step of MAELSTROM's Joint Strategy and Plan for Networking Actions on marine litter. It is based on the first year of MAELSTROM's stakeholders' engagement activities. Further stakeholder engagement activities such as specific webinars, forum discussions and demonstrative events are expected to provide additional information. Such activities will provide the means to map the Best Practices for Marine Litter removal and valorisation (deliverable D 7.2.), expected to happen on month 40 and which should be seen as part of the present Strategy.

3.1 Forum

MAELSTROM's Forum was designed as a think tank, encouraging interactive discussions to address marine litter research, initiatives and policies happening in the European space and beyond. Leveraging on past and ongoing ML projects and on practitioner's experiences and *lessons learned*, the Forum aims at becoming an international platform for knowledge sharing regarding ML mitigation efforts.

To date, several stakeholders representing society sectors have joined the Forum and it is expected that the number of registered users will increase as the project evolves. Participation in the Forum requires mandatory registration through the compilation of a form.

The Forum's structure is organized into five topics, which represent the full circular economy cycle to be discussed during the four years of the project, as follows:

- **Science and society** - Working together to address the Marine Litter (ML) challenge

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- **Localize and Characterize** - Strategies and innovative modelling to track ML and identify hotspots
- **Collect and Remove** - Innovative technologies and solutions to collect and remove ML from the coastal and marine ecosystems
- **Sort and Transform** - Marine Litter and Circular Economy: Sort and Recycling ML
- **Marketize** - Exploitation of regenerated products: best practices

Each of the topics will be analysed through a dedicated webinar with the participation of speakers and experts in the field. Highlights from webinars' discussions and conclusions will then be published on the Forum both as a repository of relevant information and as a way to promote further interactions among participants and stakeholders.

The first of five webinars (section 1.2.), held on November 18th, 2021, was dedicated to the first topic "*Science and society: Working together to address the Marine Litter (ML) challenge*" and treated the following themes: i) Civic engagement, networking and communication; ii) Stakeholder coordination; iii) Governance and iv) Funding. Open questions for each theme were discussed during the webinar and are being followed up by further interactions in the MAELSTROM Forum hosted on the project's website.

As MAELSTROM evolves the Forum will work as a platform to improve porosity between policy, industry, and society, focusing on research needs, priority actions and existing gaps in policy and societal engagement regarding marine litter. The overall goal is to contribute to a European and global collective effort to effectively address the marine litter challenge, through improved communication, networking and added-value synergies. The results from future Forum discussions and webinars will furthermore contribute to map the Best Practices for Marine Litter removal and valorisation, deliverable D 7.2. of Work Package 7 foreseen in month 40.

3.2. Webinar

Within the United Nations Ocean Decade Laboratories, under the call "A Clean Ocean," the MAELSTROM team organized a "satellite activity". The event was held on November 18th, 2021, during a one-day online seminar which engaged a total of 63 participants (Figure 1), in representation of international key-sectors: Academia, Industry, Environmental NGOs and Civil society being the majority (Figure 2). As for gender representation, 65 % of the participants were women while 43% were men.

Figure 1- Country of origin of webinar participants

Figure 2 - Sectorial representation of webinar participants

During the morning part of the webinar representatives of multi-scale marine litter related projects and initiatives presented the outcomes of efforts being implemented worldwide. Speakers represented the following institutions and/or initiatives:

- World Wildlife Fund Global - Global scale
- BlueMed Initiative – Regional scale
- The Portuguese Plastics Pact - National scale
- World Wildlife Fund Philippines - National scale
- Open Science Hub (Portugal) - Local scale
- marGnet project (Italy) - Local scale

The morning part also included a keynote speech from Thomais Vlachogianni (MIO – ECSDE³) on “*The importance and challenges of turning science into policies for*

³ [MIO-ECSDE | Mediterranean Information Office for Environment, Culture and Sustainable Development](#)

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effective actions to slash marine litter pollution, while also breaking away from a throwaway society”.

During the afternoon, the webinar followed a participatory approach around the four themes which were openly discussed among panellists and participants. The discussion was moderated by the MAELSTROM team and supported by Sli.do, a technological tool to facilitate participant’s engagement during online events. Themes and questions were the following:

- **Civic engagement, networking and communication:** *What are the biggest challenges in engaging citizens in effective and responsible behaviours (e.g., single use plastic consumerism and use)?*
- **Stakeholder coordination:** *What can be done to align multi-level stakeholders (industry, science, technology, and civil society organizations) in the implementation of common and effective solutions regarding the marine litter issue?*
- **Governance:** *What can be done to better engage decision makers in designing and implementing global, national and local regimes (legal settings, legislation, policies, frameworks, etc.) conducive to coping with marine litter removal and recycling?*
- **Funding:** *What could be the best approach to funding long-lasting results to reduce litter accumulated in marine ecosystems and to promote an effective blue circular economy?*

The participatory discussion was followed by a final wrap-up by Thomais Vlachogianni, on the main webinar outcomes and contributions to tackle marine litter in the next decade. Key messages were:

- ✓ There is the need to improve communication to effectively engage and network key-societal actors from different sectors such as industry, research, public institutions, and civil society. Thus, efforts should go into uniformizing communication through the standardization of methodologies, terminologies, and strategies. On the other hand, civic engagement should be based on a balance among scientific and emotional approaches, emphasizing positive actions and aiming at creating citizen’s ownership regarding marine litter solutions and behaviours.
- ✓ Stakeholders should be considered agents of knowledge and change. Evidence of benefits and opportunities within a governance system, promoting different priorities at distinct levels and timeframes should be widely and effectively communicated to consolidate the connection and coordination among stakeholders and their efforts.
- ✓ Decision-makers and the scientific community must invest in vision alignments and coordinated efforts regarding ML: while governments and decision makers need to get closer to the scientific processes and create open dialogues with stakeholders, the scientific community should also put

efforts into translating their findings through communicative-friendly approaches to decision makers and the public. There is also the need to invest in harmonized frameworks from local to global scales (e.g., global agencies versus communities).

- ✓ Mid- and long-term financial support is crucial to create synergies among good legacies achieved by previous actions. It is thus vital to create new funding opportunities based on previous knowledge. To promote these opportunities, governments and decision makers should implement policies to support regular funding to proven positive initiatives, while also incentivizing the involvement of new stakeholders and ideas.

4. Marine Litter and Plastic Pollution: where do we stand?

4.1. Marine litter definition

In the 2005 UNEP's report "*Marine Litter - An Analytical overview*" (2005) marine litter was defined as being "any persistent, manufactured or processed solid material discarded, disposed of or abandoned in the marine and coastal environment. Marine litter consists of items that have been made or used by people and deliberately discarded into the sea or rivers or on beaches; brought indirectly to the sea with rivers, sewage, storm water or winds; accidentally lost, including material lost at sea in bad weather (fishing gear, cargo); or deliberately left by people on beaches and shores."

Definitions advanced by other worldwide organizations converge with the above-mentioned UNEP's definition. A similar definition was proposed by the National Ocean Service-National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration in 2011, defining marine litter as being "any persistent solid material that is manufactured or processed and directly or indirectly, intentionally or unintentionally, disposed of or abandoned into the marine environment or the Great Lakes" (NOAA, 2021). Also, the OSPAR Convention in 2019 defined marine litter as "any solid material which has been deliberately discarded or unintentionally lost on beaches, on shores or at sea".

In this regard, marine debris is considered as synonymous of marine litter by UNEP's Honolulu Strategy (2011) and by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA); in this document we will be using mainly the term marine litter.

4.2. Marine litter sources

Presently, marine litter can be found in all world oceans and coastal ecosystems, posing environmental, economic, and social implications (Ryan et al., 2021).

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The first studies and reports on marine litter date back to the early 1970s (Carpenter and Smith, 1972). Since then, research has increased exponentially, highlighting the need to categorize not only sources but also the composition of marine litter (Woods et al., 2021; Schneider et al., 2018). On this regard, the United Nations Environmental Programme has identified two main ML sources: land-based sources and marine-based sources: **land-based sources** include landfills and littering of beaches and coastal areas (tourism), rivers and floodwaters, industrial emissions, discharge from storm water drains and untreated municipal sewerage (UNEP, 2009, Madricardo et al., 2020); **marine-based** sources include cargo and passenger shipping, recreational boating, military navigation, fishing and aquaculture gear, and the marine energy industry, as well as legal and illegal dumping (Čulin and Bielić, 2016).

As mentioned above, besides knowing the ML sources is also crucial to understand the composition of the items creating marine litter so to study their impacts on ecosystems and to identify appropriate actions and tools for its collection, sorting and recycling (Schneider et al., 2018). The recent UNEP report "*From Pollution to Solution. A global assessment of marine litter and plastic pollution*" (2021) reveals that the main items found on floating marine litter hotspots are: plastic drinks bottles, caps and lids (24 per cent), cigarette butts (21.8 per cent), cotton buds (13.5 per cent) and balloons and balloon sticks (2.7 per cent). As for ML accumulation on the seabed, there is still a considerable lack of knowledge since, although waste input is constantly increasing, the sea floor is still a very poorly studied environment. Sampling and modelling efforts in this field must therefore be strengthened (UNEP, 2021).

Similarly, there is also a considerable limited knowledge on the role of rivers and estuaries in the transport of litter to the ocean especially due to the lack of methodologies' standardization and limited available data. Several research studies summarized in the above-mentioned UNEP's report (2021), highlight riverine waters and sediments as being major pathways for marine litter. Back in 2015 Jambeck et al. estimated that riverine inputs from mismanaged solid waste set the amount of marine litter at 12.7 million metric tons (MT) per year while recently, Mai et al. (2020) estimated that 57,000–265,000 MT of plastic entered the oceans from riverine systems. The study used a model based on the Human Development Index (HDI) and considered key indicators to estimate global riverine waste outflows (Pinheiro et al., 2021). The same study, using worldwide data from 2018, estimated that Asian rivers accounted for approximately 69% of the total global input, with the remainder inputs coming from South America (13%), North America (7.1%), Central America (5.5%), Europe (5%), and Africa and Oceania (0.5%). On this regard, research study conducted by Schmidt et al. (2017), based on worldwide available data of plastic debris in rivers, revealed that plastic loads on large rivers disproportionately increase in relationship to the increase of plastic debris available for transport.

Based on the state of the art, there is the need for more studies and investments to understand the rivers and estuaries waste inputs contributions and sources, which is essential to inform decision-makers on adequate policies and measures.

4.3. Marine litter impacts

The accumulated anthropogenic litter in oceans and coastal areas is leading to severe impacts on ecosystems, including worldwide biodiversity losses while also compromising marine ecosystems services (Woods et al., 2021). Ecological impacts include sea life ingestion, entanglement, debris colonization and its direct and indirect toxicological effects (Beaumont et al., 2019). In addition, marine litter is also having implications on societal and economy systems. Some examples include a decline on fisheries productivity and losses on the tourism sector (Fadееva and Van Berkel, 2021).

On this regard, Woods et al. (2021) note that in some sites ML is causing a reduction of the touristic economic value due to visual pollution which is translating into an economic decline (Munari et al. 2015; Pasternak et al. 2017; UNEP 2017; Petrolia et al. 2019; Williams and Rangel-Buitrago 2019).

According to UNEP (2021), the Mediterranean region is the fourth largest producer of plastic articles in the world, generating 24 million tons of plastic waste per year. Along the trade routes, marine litter affects the entire Mediterranean blue economy, with regional economic losses estimated at 700 million dollars a year. Besides environmental and economic impacts, there is also the potential for marine litter, especially plastics and microplastics, to end up in the human food supply with inevitable consequences for human health (Barboza et al., 2020). Known routes of exposure include ingestion, inhalation, and dermal contact, with potential particle toxic effects (Prata et al., 2020).

Another impact and consequence related to ML which must be addressed is climate change. It is widely known that marine litter, especially plastics, contributes to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from the beginning to the end of its life cycle (Ford et al., 2021). Moreover, climate change is leading to a change in ocean circulation which affects the distribution of marine litter in seas around the world, making impact, distribution, and modelling studies difficult to develop (Welden and Lusher, 2017). On the other hand, cascading effects, such as natural-hazards related disasters and epidemic diseases might also lead to an increase of plastic production as recently observed with the Covid-19 pandemic. As disposable face masks (single use) are used to slow down the transmission rate of Covid-19 from person to person, this has led to a massive production of polymer-based masks, presenting a new environmental challenge for waste management. If not correctly disposed, these types of devices end up accumulating in coastal ecosystems and will later become new marine litter (Fadare and Okoffo, 2020; Woods et al., 2021; Ford et al., 2021).

During the last decade research projects have focused mainly on the ML accumulated in coastal areas and floating on the surface while monitoring and removal from the seabed remains problematic (Galgani, 2015; Schneider et al., 2018; Schwarz et al., 2019, Madricardo, 2020). For this reason, the United Nations Environmental Programme calls for further efforts on investigating the seafloor as about 70% of marine litter is estimated to sink to the bottom of the sea and the consequences are still unknown (UNEP, 2005; Madricardo, 2020).

4.4. EU Legislation and Policies for Marine Litter

Since the adoption of the Barcelona Convention in 1976, the EU has launched a series of international commitments, legislation, and measures to address the problem of marine litter, providing guidance for stakeholders and policy makers through common goals, indicators, and recommended actions. To date, the main EU strategies, and legislation on marine litter on the coastal and marine environment are:

- **The Barcelona Convention**

The Barcelona Convention was adopted in 1976 within the Mediterranean Action Plan, the first-ever Regional Seas Programme, led by UNEP. The signatory Countries agreed on cooperating to *"take all appropriate measures to prevent, abate and to the fullest possible extent eliminate pollution of the Mediterranean Sea Area.."* (art 5) whether land or sea-based sources to protect the marine and coastal environment. The Convention also developed seven Protocols on specific aspects, such as the Dumping Protocol and the Land-based sources and activities Protocol (LBS), both related to marine litter.

- **MED POL**

The MED POL program (1996) was designed for the assessment and control of marine pollution in the Mediterranean and it was the first operational program that promoted the cooperation of the countries bordering the Mediterranean to implement the three main protocols of the Barcelona Convention on waste - Dumping, Land-based sources (LBS) and Hazardous Waste Protocol. The aim is to adopt harmonized measures for the management of action plans on waste and the progressive elimination of pollution of the coastal and marine environment.

- **Regional Plan on Marine Litter Management**

The Regional Plan on Marine Litter Management in the Mediterranean (2014), adopted by the contracting Countries of Barcelona Convention, is the first plan that is totally based on the Ecosystem Approach values to achieve Good Environment Status (GES). The Mediterranean Region aims to set legally binding actions to prevent and reduce marine litter pollution in the Mediterranean Sea, alongside its impact on habitats, species (with special focus on the ones classified as threatened), public health and safety. Another relevant goal is to implement a "fishing for litter" system.

- **EU Integrated Maritime Policy (IMP)**

The Integrated Maritime Policy (IMP) of the European Union (EU) is a holistic approach to all sea-related EU policies. It is based on the idea that the EU can draw higher returns from its maritime space with less impact on the environment by coordinating its wide range of interlinked activities related to oceans, seas and coasts. Hence, the IMP aims at strengthening the so-called blue economy, encompassing all sea-based economic activities - including tourism, fishing, and maritime transport - while covering the following policy fields: i) Blue growth; ii) Marine data and knowledge; iii) Maritime spatial planning; iv) Integrated maritime surveillance, v) Sea basin strategies.

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- **Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)**

The MSFD is a binding legal instrument for assessing, monitoring, and setting targets for reaching and/or maintaining the Good Environmental Status (GES) of all EU marine waters. It sets the framework and objectives for Member States (MS) for their marine waters for prevention, protection and conservation of the marine environment from spoiling human activity. The MSFD Good Environmental Status (GES) was expected to be achieved by 2020 considering 11 qualitative indicators. Indicator number 10 addressed the issue of marine litter, aiming for "*properties and quantities of marine litter do not cause harm to the coastal and marine environment*". A Technical Group (TG) was set up to perform this specific indicator's evaluation. GES was not achieved yet.

- **Water Framework Directive (WFD)**

The Water Framework Directive (WFD) called for all inland water bodies (rivers and lakes), groundwater, estuaries and coastal waters to achieve or maintain Good Ecological Status by 2015 (goal not achieved as scheduled). WFD includes the design and implementation of a program of measures, some of which are related to marine litter management. It also should contribute to the MSFD's goal to achieve the Good Environmental Status by 2020 for marine waters.

- **EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy**

Adopted in 2015, the EU Action Plan for Circular Economy identified plastics as a key priority and committed itself to '*prepare a strategy addressing the challenges posed by plastics throughout the value chain, considering their entire lifecycle*'. On this regard, the Plan sets long-term targets to increase preparation for reuse and recycling of key waste streams such as origin from packaging industry.

- **EU Commission Strategy of Plastics in a Circular Economy**

Published in the beginning of 2018, the Strategy addresses the environmental leakages of plastics and microplastics, including issues of recyclability, biodegradability, and presence of hazardous substances.

- **Directive 2019/904/ EC on Single-Use Plastics**

Published in 2019, the directive promotes circular approaches that give priority to sustainable and non-toxic re-usable products and re-use systems rather than to single-use products, aiming first and foremost to reduce the quantity of waste generated. Main goal is "*to prevent and reduce the impact of certain plastic products on the environment, in particular the aquatic environment, and on human health, as well as to promote the transition to a circular economy with innovative and sustainable business models, products and materials, thus also contributing to the efficient functioning of the internal market*".

Other EU directives and policies related to marine litter management include:

- **Directive 91/271/EEC (amend 98/15/EC) on Urban Wastewater Treatment**

As the discharge of urban wastewater is one of the sources of marine litter the directive set indications regarding sewage related marine debris including, among other things, condoms, sanitary towels, tampons, and plastic cotton wool bud

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sticks. Micro-plastics and fibbers from clothes washing and storm water overflows are also significant sources of marine litter which were addressed by the directive.

- **Directive 94/62/EC (amend 2015/720/EU) on Packaging and Packaging Waste**
Sets a range of requirements to reduce the impact of packaging and packaging waste on the environment. It also requires reducing the use of light-weight plastic carrier bags and presenting a report examining the environmental impact of the use of oxo-degradable plastic bags. The amended version required MS to take measures to reduce the consumption by the end of 2019 and that the annual threshold would not exceed 90 plastic bags per person using economic instruments such as taxes, marketing restrictions or prohibiting free plastic bags.

- **Directive 94/62/EC (amend 2015/720/EU) on Reducing the Consumption of Plastic Carry Bags (Plastic bags directive)**
It requires reducing the use of light-weight plastic carrier bags and presenting a report examining the environmental impact of the use of oxo-degradable plastic bags. Amended version requires MS to take measures to reduce the consumption by the end of 2019 that the annual threshold does not exceed 90 plastic bags per person; this goal can be achieved using economic instruments such as taxes, marketing restrictions or prohibiting free plastic bags.

- **Directive 1999/31/EC on Landfill Waste (Landfill Directive)**
Establishes technical requirements for the operation of landfills, with the goal of reducing their impact on the environment, including the pollution of surface water. It requires that the location of landfill sites considers factors such as the proximity to water bodies and coastal waters, and that wind-blown materials are minimized. Such measures should reduce potential dispersal of plastic packaging waste and other debris in the marine environment.

- **Directive 2008/98/EC on Waste Framework**
Sets out essential conditions for waste management for all waste and established key principles and requirements for the management of plastic packaging waste. It introduces a binding waste hierarchy: at the top of the list is waste prevention, followed by re-use, recycling and then other recovery operations, with disposal such as sending waste to landfill as the last resort. From 2018 on, an amendment to the Directive included a set of measures to stop marine litter production, especially from land-based activities.

- **Directive 2009/125/EC on Ecodesign**
It aims to improve design on a product specific level by eliminating the worst performing products from the market and shifting the economy towards solutions with the least life-cycle costs.

- **Commission Decision 2014/8937EU on Ecological Criteria for the Award of the EU Ecolabel for Rinse-off Cosmetic Products**
It includes microplastics in "Specified Excluded ingoing substances and mixtures" banning microplastics from being included in Ecolabel products in any form.

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4.5. United Nations 2030 Agenda

The marine litter issue is also clearly addressed on the UN 2030 Agenda⁴, through **SDG 14 Life Below Water**, specifically by achieving Target 14.1: *"by 2025, prevent and significantly reduce marine pollution of all kinds, from land-based activities, including marine debris and nutrient pollution"*.

The absence of marine litter and pollution, with focus on *abandoned, lost or otherwise discarded fishing gear* (ALDFG) is considered by SDG 14 to be a critical milestone for marine good environmental status. Nonetheless, the marine litter challenge relates also to other SDG's: based on the Ocean Care report "Marine debris and the Sustainable Development Goals⁵", the nexus among marine litter and the sustainable development goals can be expressed as follows:

SDG 2 Zero Hunger: Target 2.3 - *"By 2030, double the agricultural productivity and incomes of small-scale food producers, in particular women, indigenous peoples, family farmers, pastoralists and fishers, including through secure and equal access to land, other productive resources and inputs, knowledge, financial services, markets and opportunities for value addition and non-farm employment"*.

The health and productivity of the oceans and of fisheries are threatened by the effect of marine litter and of ALDFG on the marine ecosystem. Another concern is that microplastics may enter the food chain through the consumption of fishery products; on the other hand, marine litter also represents a hazard for navigation through the risk of collisions (Macfadyen, 2009).

SDG 6 Clear Water and Sanitation: Target 6.3 - *"By 2030, improve water quality by reducing pollution, eliminating dumping and minimizing release of hazardous chemicals and materials, halving the proportion of untreated wastewater and substantially increasing recycling and safe reuse globally"*.

Efficient solutions to reduce and prevent waste from land-based sources entering the marine ecosystem through riverways will have impacts on water safety and quality.

SDG 8 Decent Work and Economic Growth: Target 8.4 - *"Improve progressively, through 2030, global resource efficiency in consumption and production and endeavour to decouple economic growth from environmental degradation"*.

The presence of plastic in the oceans causes economic losses which are proportional to the quantity of marine litter in the ecosystem. Losses include cost with beach clean-ups and within the fisheries, tourism and navigation sectors

SDG 9 Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure: Target 9.4 - *"By 2030, upgrade infrastructure and retrofit industries to make them sustainable, with increased resource-use efficiency and greater adoption of clean and environmentally sound technologies and industrial processes, with all countries taking action in accordance with their respective capabilities"*.

Inefficient waste management leads to an increase in the amount of plastic waste entering the marine ecosystem. It is therefore necessary to allocate significant

⁴ <https://sdgs.un.org/>

⁵ http://www.oceancare.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Marine_Debris_neutral_2018_web.pdf

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investments for middle- and low-income countries in waste management infrastructure.

SDG 12 Sustainable Cities and Communities: Target 12.5 - *“By 2030, substantially reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse”*.

In the short term, it is urgent to improve waste collection and management in developing countries. In the long term, the goal is to achieve a circular blue economy in which single-use plastics are eliminated and the packaging is minimized. In other intermediate cases it may be necessary to supplement existing laws with bans on certain products and practices.

5. Current landscape on Marine Litter research and technology, societal behaviour and international cooperation

With marine litter being considered as one of the most meaningful environmental crises of the beginning of the new century it is of utmost importance to create cross-sectorial synergies among science, industry, society, and decision-makers for durable solutions.

The present section makes a brief description of the current landscape regarding marine litter, based on a brief literature review on:

- Research on ML and development of blue technologies for removal and prevention
- Societal behavioural change and citizen science to reduce ML and support circular/blue economy
- International cooperation and capacity building for ML removal and mitigation actions

Focus is given to main achievements, future perspectives, and remaining gaps for each action area.

5.1. Research on ML and development of blue technologies for removal and prevention

The first research article reporting the environmental impact of marine litter was published in the 1960s when Kenyon and Kridler (1969) described the ingestion of marine litter items by Laysan Albatrosses on the northwest Hawaiian Islands. Further awareness of the threats posed by plastic pollution to marine ecosystems developed gradually through the 1960s and 1970s, with environmental impacts developed during the 1980s resulting in numerous policy discussions and recommendations aimed at decreasing the amount and impact of marine litter (Chen 2015). Exponential growth in both field and laboratory multidisciplinary research, education and public outreach was observed after the new millennium decade.

The anthropogenic litter issue has since then received much attention, having recently been recognized as a serious global environmental concern (Bellou et al.,

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2021). The latest UNEP report on marine litter (2021) highlights the fact that the impacts of marine litter on world aquatic ecosystems health are leading to a wide range of social and economic consequences, such as loss of revenue from natural resources and damage to maritime industries and coastal infrastructures (UNEP, 2021). Marine litter is thus presently seen as a complex and multi-dimensional challenge (Chassignet et al., 2021). On this regard, Madricardo et al (2020) suggest a multilevel approach for coordinating actions to minimize, prevent or avoid environmental, economic and social losses resulting from inadequate marine litter management strategies. The suggested approach covers various aspects such as the evaluation of the macro litter on the seabed, the identification of accumulation hotspots, the removal and recycling procedures and strategies for stakeholders and citizens' engagement.

Research on marine litter has so far been focused on six major topics: i) distribution and composition of marine litter, ii) interaction with marine biota, iii) toxic effects, iv) horizontal and vertical transport, v) social aspects and vi) degradation of marine plastic litter (Hidalgo-Ruz and Thiel, 2015). However, some research gaps remain. According to the United Nations Environmental Programme report (2021), **there is still a considerable lack of scientific knowledge on marine litter aquatic distribution and sources, due to a limited standardization of monitoring methodologies and protocols and the lack of knowledge on the seabed, specially the deep-seabed.** Past surveys and monitoring efforts demonstrated that the ocean and currents control the distribution and accumulation of floating marine litter, however, observational data is still very scarce and sparse, making it challenging to identify marine litter sources and to develop ocean circulation models to predict the debris movements (van Sebille et al., 2020, Bellou et al., 2021; UNEP, 2021). Other gaps include the **potential long-term climate effects on marine litter production and distribution, marine litter health impacts on marine organisms and humans (e.g., via seafood consumption), and the social and economic medium-long-term costs from the ecosystem services losses.** According to Hahladakis (2020) the implementation of effective and long-term monitoring protocols and integrated multidisciplinary programs regarding the environmental impact of marine litter in the oceans and on human health is of utmost importance but this will require more critical integrated thinking, so to support governance and enhance the return of research results as policy-informing and operational knowledge (Fanini et al., 2021).

Alongside the growth in research, several technologies were also developed for marine monitoring, including litter. Examples include unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) equipped with several types of cameras such as infrared cameras, RGB video cameras and LIDAR installed in manned aircraft and satellite imagery (Garcia-Garin et al., 2020). Remote sensing technologies have been considered one of the most affordable and low-cost science-based solutions to integrate in situ monitoring (Maximenko et al., 2019), while also providing data and tools to a diversity of societal actors such as I&D institutions, decision-makers and governments addressing marine litter.

However, alongside the importance of developing multidisciplinary approaches to map and understand the impacts of marine litter, there is also an urgency to invest in its prevention and mitigation. Selection and removal activities, in general but especially within marine environments, should be conducted in such a way that the

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benefits are greater than the damage caused (Da Ros et al., 2016). Nevertheless, the recent UNEP's report (2021) states that so far, **solutions for marine litter removal, specially from the seabed, have been considered either highly harmful for the marine ecosystem (dredges or bottom trawl nets) or inefficient (ROV, divers)**, (UNEP 2021). Alternative solutions include: i) cost-effective in situ cleaning methods located preferably near the marine litter major sources; ii) technologies to limit the amount of litter entering the sea, for example through the improvement of wastewater treatment facilities (Frantzi et al., 2021).

On this regard, the MAELSTROM project will implement two innovative technologies: an underwater cable robot for the removal of marine litter on the seabed of the Venice Lagoon (Italy) and a Bubble Barrier to catch floating plastics from water column in the Ave River (Portugal), preventing it from reaching the sea. These activities will be based and followed by high standard environmental and impact assessments.

Several other marine litter removal technologies (Table 1 and Table 2) have been developed during the last decade, taking into account the different size of the waste, ranging from filters to physical barriers. Examples include: The Trash Wheel, Seabin Smart Tech, Thomsea (Winterstetter et al. 2021), Archimedean Drum Screw and the SEEKer Robot (InNoPlastic project⁶). All of them aim at recycling the full set of retrieved waste into higher value materials whose characteristics, performance and economic value are assessed for future marketization.

Even though the development of new removal technologies is very recent, with data on mid- and long-term effects on the environment to still be followed by regular and standardized scientific monitoring actions, they represent a turning point in marine litter removal efforts and thus, should be put on top of international agendas. However, removal technologies alone will not solve the marine litter problem: recent evidence highlights **the need to combine removal technologies with people-oriented practices and to involve relevant stakeholders in the valorisation of captured debris within a full circular economy approach** (Winterstetter et al., 2021).

⁶ Innovative approaches towards prevention, removal and reuse of marine plastic litter; <https://www.innoplactic.eu/>.

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Table 2 - Examples of mechanical technologies developed during the last decade within worldwide and EU projects to tackle marine litter.

Project/Initiatives	Tools	Technology/Innovation
<u>MAELSTROM</u>	GEES technology	Hot pressing of hardly recyclable litter
	Cable based underwater robot	Installed and operated from a floating barge it uses different tools: a dredge to collect small items laying on the seabed and floating in the water column; a gripper and hook to grasp larger items which are deposited in a basket, itself lifted on the floating platform by a crane.
	Bubble Barrier	Collects submerged items in the water column and from the water surface in rivers. Will be implemented by the first time in a estuary.
<u>InNoPlastic</u>	Mobile drum screw filters	Screw filters filter litter and macroplastics while letting fish enter and exit safely.
	SEEker	Autonomous vehicle equipped with robotic hands able to collect plastic waste from beaches.
<u>CLAIM</u>	Floating barriers	Floating barriers prevent different kinds of plastics to enter the sea
	Ferry Box	Automated seawater sampling device coupled with a passive flow-through filtering system, installed on ships.
<u>River Cleaning</u>	River Cleaning	Intelligent floating modular barrier intercepts floating waste in streams through rotation.
<u>OMD - Veritas</u>	EcoCat	Fully electric catamaran with a conveyor belt collects floating plastic and transports it into a removable bin unloadable with a mechanism located on the top of the boat.
<u>The Trash Wheel</u>	The Trash Wheel	Semi-autonomous trash interceptor lifts litter out of the water and onto his conveyor belt.
<u>Everwave</u>	CollectiX	Rubbish collection boat which can smartly analyse the garbage and collect marine litter through a conveyor belt.
<u>Thomsea</u>	Thomsea	By drawing on the natural power of water and thanks to its trawls, it removes litter from rivers and seas.
<u>Fish Flow Innovation</u>	Archimedean Drum Screw	Innovative rotary drum screen that effectively separates solid objects from the intake water. Its characteristics let fish return unharmed to surface waters and reduce the costs for the processing of solid wastes.
<u>Seabin Smart Project</u>	Seabin Smart Tech	Seabin Smart Tech is a rubbish bin in the water. The catch bag V5 Hybrid works as a filter for both macro and micro floating waste. It is made by a 100% recyclable plastic mesh.

Table 3 - Examples of chemical technologies developed during the last decade within worldwide and EU projects to tackle marine litter

Project/Initiatives	Tools	Technology/Innovation	Outputs
<u>marGnet</u>	Innovative prototype	Uses low temperature pyrolysis for the synthesis of marine fuels out of marine litter.	Marine diesel fuel complying with ISO 8217 DMA and DMB class.
<u>MAELSTROM</u>	Innovative prototype	Pyrolysis waste-to-energy plant synthesizes marine fuels out of marine litter.	Fuel used to co-supply the project raft energy demands.
	Innovative prototype	Additivation with organic or recycled fibres.	Transformation of degraded low-quality thermoplastics into high performance Composites.
<u>InNoPlastic</u>	Syngas	Direct and indirect gasification and pyrolysis.	Electrical and thermal energy in combined-cycles and delivery energy.
	SepaRaptor	Uses of ultrasounds to compress nano and micro-plastics together to make it easier to retrieve bigger pieces of plastics from the water.	
<u>CLAIM</u>	Photocatalytic device	Sorts micro-plastics.	
<u>GOJELLY</u>	Bio-based filter obtained from the jellyfish mucus	Absorbs nano and micro-plastics using bio-based filters.	

5.2. Societal behavioural change and citizen science to reduce ML and to support a circular and blue economy

The practice of public participation and collaboration in scientific research can produce relevant outcomes when it comes to addressing the marine litter challenge. According to Campbell et al. (2019), questions relating to the volume of plastics in the oceans, where it accumulates, the process of how plastics break down into microplastics or how it affects ecosystems, require new ways of collecting and analysing data. In this regard, if properly set, citizen science and **community activities, like targeted clean-ups and plastic's source identification represent a useful and cost-effective mechanism of data collection, while also being an opportunity to raise awareness** (Campbell, 2019).

Global initiatives such as the Earth Challenge 2020, Marine Debris Trackers and Marine Litter Watch are some examples of successful citizen-science initiatives which include not only the physical removal of litter but also its primary source identification, pathways and accumulation zones.

The last UNEP report on ML (2021) states that despite not having yet globally standardized protocols, citizen-science and community initiatives such as beach clean-ups have contributed to the increase in data availability on marine litter, while also leading to technological tools such as mobile apps which have furthermore stimulated the active engagement of citizens.

Collaboration in citizen science requires scientists and researchers to work, network and engage with community-based groups. Pursued activities and data collected within these processes often represent an added-value resource for data modelling activities on ML distribution and can be useful to better understand impacts on local ecosystems and societal wellbeing.

Within this collaborative process, all society actors should be considered, from civil society organizations (CSO) to educational structures (schools). A survey conducted within the EU funded MARLISCO project - MARine Litter in European Seas: Social Awareness and CO-Responsibility - found that young generations are key targets to raise awareness on the issue of waste reduction, as they can influence their environment in a direct and immediate way (through peers and family members) as well as being the future generation of decision-makers (Orthodoxou, 2014).

The tables below summarize some key citizen-science and community initiatives relevant to the present strategy.

Table 4 - Examples of international level citizen-science and community initiatives

Organization	Initiative	Aim
World Wildlife Fund (WWF)	No Plastics in Nature Initiative	The "No Plastics in Nature" initiative aims to stop the flow of plastic entering nature by 2030 through three main actions: i) the elimination of unnecessary plastic; ii) doubling reuse, recycling, and recovery rates; iii) ensuring the remaining plastic is sourced responsibly. This initiative focuses on areas such as corporate engagement monitoring through citizen science and campaigns for public awareness. It is supported and co-designed by several WWF Offices (i.e., Norway, US, Netherlands, Germany, UK, China, Singapore, Philippines, Indonesia, Vietnam, Thailand, Hong Kong).
European Environment Agency (EEA)	Marine Litter Watch	Marine Litter Watch combines citizen engagement and modern technology to help tackle marine litter. It is designed to support data collection events on beaches and other stretches of coast in all regional seas in Europe.
EU-Citizen Science consortium	Plastic Pirates – Go Europe!	"Plastic Pirates – Go Europe!" is an international citizen science campaign launched by the ministries of education, science and research of Germany, Portugal, and Slovenia. The goal is to raise awareness on the importance of protecting our rivers as natural resources and to highlight the value added of international research collaboration. The campaign calls upon children and adolescents aged between 10 and 16 years to investigate the subject of plastic waste in the environment, particularly in and near various bodies of waters, through several sample campaigns
GeoTech Innovations	OpenLitterMap	OpenLitterMap is an open source, interactive and accessible database regarding the world's litter and plastic pollution. Users can add new data and/or download existing data for free and use it for any purpose. Users are invited to take pictures of the collected litter, tag it and describe if the litter was picked up or not.
EARTHDAY.ORG	Global Earth Challenge	Global Earth Challenge™ seeks to become the world's largest coordinated citizen science campaign by developing a new mobile application for data collection and a platform for global citizen science data. The mobile app calls for people around the world to monitor threats to environmental and human health in their communities. A new open data platform will make it easier for researchers around the world to find and access high-quality information and use citizen science data for international policy assessments like the U.N. Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
PADI	Dive Against Debris®	Through PADI's flagship program, the Dive Against Debris® (DAD®) initiative, the largest underwater citizen science database for marine debris on the planet was created. The diver takes direct 'fins on' action for the ocean, collecting critical survey data that can be used by marine researchers and policymakers for conservation efforts.
Adventure Scientists	Global Microplas	Within the Global Microplastics Initiative, Adventure Scientists mobilized thousands of trained volunteers

	tics Initiative	to help identify the extent of microplastic pollution in marine and freshwater systems around the world. This has led to the creation of one of the largest global microplastic pollution datasets which is being used by businesses, governments, and individuals to limit plastic waste.
Ellipsis Earth	Ellipsis Earth	Ellipsis Earth harnesses the power of technology to identify, map and track litter in the environment. The data generated is critically used on decision-making, by providing information on trends and impacts of environmental pollution around the world. Ellipsis Earth also champions effective science communication, telling the right stories to the right audiences to create the most lasting impact.

Table 5 - Examples of national level citizen-science and community initiatives

Organization	Initiative	Aim
Portuguese Association of Marine Waste (APLM)	Edumar	The project “Edumar- know to protect” promotes diversity of resources and activities for Ocean Literacy, with the concern to adapt them to the Portuguese reality. The project co-creates resources and activities in partnership with schools.
	How much litter is on your beach?	“How much litter is on your beach?” is awareness raising project for citizens aiming at developing and App to monitor marine litter in beaches, contributing to share data obtained with the scientific community.
Tangaroa Blue Foundation	Australian Marine Debris Initiative	Tangaroa Blue Foundation is an Australia-wide not-for-profit organisation dedicated to the removal and prevention of marine debris. It created the Australian Marine Debris Initiative (AMDl), a network of communities, schools, industries, government agencies and individuals focused on reducing the number of marine debris washing into our oceans. This initiative includes actions such as clean-ups, monitoring programs, workshops on mitigation strategies and educational resources and materials.
Litterati	Litterati	Litterati is building a platform that empowers people to create better solutions regarding litter and waste issues. Cities, corporations, NGOs and schools are engaged on the identification of collected litter, describing the object, its material, and brand. People and groups involved are encouraged to participate in data collection through the LitterAI App, to manage clean-up events and to bring activities into classrooms.

Table 6 - Examples of local level citizen-science and community initiatives

Organization	Initiative	Aim
Open Science Hub – Portugal	Figueira Circular	Figueira Circular promotes promote a Circular Economy system that rewards the reuse of waste and its transformation into value-added products, through the creation of a local currency (Sustento). The project promotes the adoption of more sustainable practices based on the efficient and lasting use of resources.

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Civic Laboratory for Environmental Action Research (CLEAR)	Marine Debris Trackers	Civic Laboratory for Environmental Action Research (CLEAR) is an interdisciplinary natural and social science lab space which has developed The Marine Debris Tracker App. For data collection, litter items must be picked up in a trash bag and logged in the app. The logged items are recorded into a public data set which can be used by scientists.
Clean Coast Bonaire	Clean Coast Bonaire	Clean Coast Bonaire is a Caribbean organization that participates in regional conversations regarding harmonization of marine litter data collection and monitoring. Data collection in the region is geographically selected to provide a good sampling of the Bonaire coastline and follow the OSPAR Marine Litter Monitoring Protocol.
The Black Bag	The Black Bag	The Black Bag is a Third Sector Entity which, thanks to the contribution of its volunteers, works to protect the environment. Events are organized as clean-ups, with particular attention to Ligurian beaches (Italy). Dissemination contents based on scientific information are produced to raise public awareness on the marine litter environmental issue.

5.3. International cooperation and capacity building for ML removal and mitigation actions

"Our ocean is connected" (UNEP, 2021)

Ocean connectivity, that enables marine life to exist and move freely, also means that human activities are likely to have global consequences. For what regards marine litter, it does not only affect the ecosystem where it enters but drifts around the globe threatening marine life worldwide⁷ (UNEP, 2021).

The connectivity of ocean life and the threats it faces requires us to adopt regional and international approaches to find solutions to the challenges faced, as countries working in isolation cannot properly address the root causes of problems affecting their local marine environments. Transboundary and international cooperation are essential to collectively address common challenges/goals and have proven to be effective in the development of innovative solutions to tackle marine litter (Napper and Thomson, 2020). When including capacity building actions, international cooperation initiatives also represent an opportunity to strengthen governmental, institutional and single capacities on addressing marine litter causes and impacts. As countries work together they reduce the global burden, enable resource pools and optimize efforts for better and long-lasting impacts.

Tackling marine litter should not be seen merely as a challenge, but also a driver of new opportunities (UN Environment, 2017; Rodic-Wiersma, 2013). Some opportunities include:

- New materials for the industry
- Job creation opportunities in marine litter prevention and management

⁷ <https://www.unep.org/news-and-stories/story/why-international-cooperation-key-preserving-worlds-oceans>

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- Increased multisectoral resources mobilization for marine litter mitigation
- New research opportunities in global assessments and on emerging issues associated with marine litter
- Synergy promotion among key stakeholders including academia, NGOs, the private sector, governments and international organizations
- Enabled complementarities between partnerships and relevant international initiatives, instruments, action plans and activities
- Enhanced frameworks and new supporting measures

However, as the international community moves forward to tackle marine litter pollution at the global level, major gaps remain (Bellou et al., 2021; Schumacher et al., 2020; Carlini et al., 2018; UNEA 2/11 resolution, 2017), including:

- The lack of a global institution leading to the coordination of existing efforts and coherence between different policies
- The lack of globally binding standards to mitigate marine pollution, in particular plastic waste originating from land-based sources
- The lack of policy implementation structures and processes
- Fragmented coverage of the existing agreements
- Rare or lacking specific decision support tools
- Limited scientific data and its harmonization
- Lack of standardization for marine debris management approaches

The Global Partnership on Marine Litter (GPML) is an international multiple stakeholder partnership, coordinated by a Steering Committee and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). It promotes cooperation and coordination between countries, through knowledge sharing and the identification of gaps and emerging issues based on stakeholders' expertise, resources and motivation to reduce and prevent marine litter and plastic pollution.

International commitments and goals, such as the GPML and SDGs, provide a good basis for worldwide effective solutions, if global frameworks are translated, adapted and followed at regional and national levels (Chen, 2015). However, the different spatial and temporal scenarios on the causes and distribution of marine litter are context-specific and complex. Thus, the design and implementation of effective, efficient and legitimate actions need to be based on a thorough understanding of the local governance context (Van Assche et al., 2014).

National capacity is an essential pillar for the forward harmonization of information at the regional and global levels, where effective policies and frameworks are decided. Here governments and policymakers have a pivotal role. One recent example was the EU decision to ban single-use plastics, including cotton buds, straws, cutlery in each member state (Directive EU2019/904 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/904/>). Effort should be put into searching for ways in which multiple initiatives strengthen each other's results towards long-lasting impacts.

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6. MAELSTROM's webinar outcomes

The first of a total of five webinars foreseen to happen during MAELSTROM was held on November 18th, 2021 and addressed the first topic "*Science and society: Working together to address the Marine Litter (ML) challenge*" (section 1.2.). The webinar was held under United Nations Ocean Decade aimed at creating a participatory discussion among practitioners and stakeholders involved in ML initiatives at local, national and global scales so to identify existing gaps and to collect suggestions to improve the following areas: i) Civic engagement, networking and communication; ii) Stakeholder coordination; iii) Governance and iv) Funding. This section presents the main outcomes from the webinar. Further information will be available on MAELSTROM's Forum⁸.

6.1. Civic engagement, networking, and communication

Question: *What are the biggest challenges in engaging citizens in effective and responsible behaviours (e.g., single use plastic consumerism and use)?*

- **Need for transboundary harmonization of waste and marine litter terminologies and management strategies**

Important gaps were identified on what regards citizen-orientated waste management terminologies and actions across countries and even in neighbouring regions within the same country. Highlights were given on the diverse ways the same type of waste is classified and on the colour of disposal bins which often differ from region to region. This aspect is seen as a driver of confusion on citizen's behaviours regarding correct plastic disposal. Another suggestion called for the translation of the disposal bins into various languages to avoid the decrease in the recycling efficiency rates observed during high-season periods on some touristic locations. Efforts thus should go into uniformizing waste and ML related communication through harmonized terminologies and strategies within and across countries.

- **Need for positive *action-related* communication**

Participants highlighted the fact that the marine litter/plastic pollution issue is often communicated *negatively*, focused on dramatic effects and irreversible losses which create a sense of disempowerment to do something about it. To promote positive results of actions carried out at any scale (from local to global), seems to be more effective by tangibly involving citizens and institutional actors to be part of the "change" needed.

Civic engagement should thus be based on a balance among scientific and emotional messages, which emphasize positive actions and create citizen's ownership on addressing the marine litter issue through positive behaviours. A good message has to be a balance of accuracy, clarity, ease and emotionality.

⁸ www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/forums/forum/maelstrom-forum/

- **Need to consider citizens as agents of knowledge and change**

According to participants, citizens' potential to become true agents of knowledge (citizen scientists) and change (activism) need to be considered. However, to be positively engaged citizens need to be involved in a project/initiative with precise objectives and where a relationship among scientists and communities is created. Events, where citizens can have an active role, such as clean-ups, monitoring activities, use of ML open-source apps and public awareness sessions in which the debate with key stakeholders can clarify procedures and objectives, are opportunities to be promoted. The message should be that everyone's contribution, within their own action areas and through their consumerism choices, is essential to address marine litter and other environmental issues.

6.2. Stakeholder coordination and cooperation

Question: *What can be done to align multi-level stakeholders (industry, science, technology, and civil society organizations) in the implementation of common and effective solutions regarding the marine litter issue?*

- **Need to align visions among scientists and institutional stakeholders**

Decision-makers and the scientific community should invest in vision's alignments and coordinated efforts regarding ML: while governments and decision makers need to get closer to the scientific processes and create open dialogues with stakeholders, the scientific community should also put efforts into translating their findings through communicative-friendly approaches to decision makers and the public. There is also the need to invest in harmonized frameworks from local to global scales (e.g., global agencies *versus* communities).

- **Need for strong networks and better coordination**

Strong cross-sectorial networks were identified as being effective platforms to engage and network actors coming from industry, research, public administration, and civil society. Networks should represent platforms where stakeholders' needs are listened to and issues are addressed in ways where all parts see beneficial outcomes, even when that means to adopt restrictive measures – in this case compensation solutions must also be planned. Stakeholders should be considered agents of change: evidence of benefits and opportunities within a governance system, promoting different priorities at distinct levels and timeframes should be widely and effectively communicated to consolidate the connection and coordination among stakeholders and their efforts.

On the other hand, networks can also work as catalysers for the compliance with international policies and frameworks, clarifying doubts and sharing best practices on how to adopt certain measures, how to report on indicators and ultimately, how to achieve international milestones.

The EU is committed to consolidate existing connections among stakeholders and to foster new ones, through better funding coordination among programmes and

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project axes in such a way as to favour the capitalization of the results obtained. On this regard, MAELSTROM and In-No-Plastic H2020 projects have set a collaborative framework where both projects are designing and implementing joint actions to capitalize efforts and synergies. Efforts to connect with other EU projects are being implemented through dedicated workshops and events.

6.3. Governance

Question: *What can be done to better engage decision makers in designing and implementing global, national and local regimes (legal settings, legislation, policies, frameworks, etc.) conducive to coping with marine litter removal and recycling?*

- Need for policy and projects' coherence

Participants noted that often there is a lack of connection among international policies and the ones acted at the national and local levels. Efforts for an increased policy-coherence were suggested as ways to support the adoption of a global framework to effectively address the marine litter issue.

On the same line, programmes and projects are often not coordinated which leads to overlaps, redundant information, and unsustainable uses of projects' outcomes (e.g., technologies not used by beneficiaries). It is important to map and capitalize successful initiatives, communicate their positive impacts, and assure their sustainability and integration with other projects on the long-term.

- Need for ML "brokers"

Participants highlighted the need to have ML brokers acting at all levels. Brokers have the function of bridging scientists, stakeholders, and citizens by translating scientific findings, numbers, and data into understandable discourses so to facilitate the adoption of science-based evidence into local policies, programs' priorities, and citizens' behaviours.

- Need for sustainable standards and policies

Some participants suggested the implementation of new sustainable standards and product quality labels based on more restrictive requirements regarding the use of plastics, their sources, uses and disposal management.

6.4. Funding

Question: *What could be the best approach to funding long-lasting results to reduce litter accumulated in marine ecosystems and to promote an effective blue circular economy?*

- Need for long-term funding

Mid and long-term financial support is crucial to create synergies among good legacies achieved by previous actions. It is thus vital to create new funding opportunities based on previous knowledge. To promote these opportunities,

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governments and decision makers should implement policies to support regular funding to proven positive initiatives, while also incentivizing the involvement of new stakeholders and ideas.

- **Need to re-fund/capitalize successful projects**

As mentioned above, priority should be given to map and capitalize successful initiatives, communicate their positive impacts, and assure their sustainability and integration with other projects on the long-term. An aligned funding scheme which incentivizes the creation of synergies among positive legacies while also promoting innovation would, according to participants, be key to achieve quicker solution to address the marine litter challenge.

- **Need to reach public-private funding opportunities**

Participants suggested that the role of the market should not be seen as an enemy but should be exploited to implement innovations and to create opportunities for new businesses that follow the principles of the circular economy. Public/private partnerships should be kept seen as an opportunity for circular economy.

- **Need to promote "glocal" approaches**

Think globally (on the challenge) act locally (on the solution). Participants highlighted the need for funding to support this concept as often smaller scale projects can have extreme positive benefits at local level. While international cooperation should still be seen as an opportunity to share knowledge and skills and to scale up innovations, local-based initiatives should also be promoted and funded as a cost-effective and climate-friendly approach to address the marine litter issue.

6.5. Wrap-Up

The following table summarizes the above-mentioned main webinar outcomes.

Table 7 - Recap of the outcomes main from MAELSTROM's webinar

<p>Civic engagement, Networking and communication</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement global, transboundary standardization on waste and marine litter terminologies and citizen's actions related with waste disposal. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote positive results and <i>action-related</i> communication. • Consider and empower citizens as agents of knowledge and change. • Promote responsible behaviours. • Engage young generations/Schools.
<p>Stakeholder coordination and cooperation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work towards aligned visions among scientists and institutional authorities. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invest in stronger and better dialogues and cross-sectorial networks and coordination mechanisms. • Use "brokers" to bridge and facilitate dialogues among stakeholders' expectations, obligations and backgrounds. • Boost concrete choices. • Set clear indicators and harmonize them with existing global and national frameworks and legal settings. • Have dedicated working groups to proper support stakeholders' diversity.
<p>Governance</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invest in policy and strategies alignment and coherence across levels and regions (avoid repetition and redundancy). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Map and capitalize successful initiatives. • Be compliant with international frameworks to address ML through adequate national and local plans, working groups and transparent reporting. • Empower the creation of new professional figures such as brokers to support science-based policy making and effective communication across stakeholders at all levels. • Implement and promote sustainable practices across sectors regarding the use of plastics, their sources, uses and disposal management plans. • Create opportunities and incentives for less environmental impactful business.

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve the actual funding schemes (2-3-years) with long-term funding approaches. • Re-fund and/or capitalize successful legacies from previous actions and promote synergies among innovations. • Promote and set public-private funding schemes for wider coverage and quicker outcomes. • Promote and invest in “glocal” initiatives, as cost effective and climate friendly solutions. • Foster international cooperation and exchange of knowledge, technologies, and skills.
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7. What is next? Suggested transformative changes regarding marine litter for the next decades

During recent years, the increased perception about marine litter stimulated policymakers to introduce changes to reduce and rethink plastic consumption and production, especially focused on disposable items. Positive trends towards marine litter reduction have in fact been observed, especially through the scaling up of stakeholder engagement and innovation and the increase in the number of voluntary commitments (UNEP, 2019). The UNEP/EA.4/11 analysis finds that governments remain at the forefront of activities to reduce marine litter and tackle plastics in the ocean, although the role of civil society and foundations is growing. Much more can be done and to build on existing mechanisms to maximize synergies, impact and efficacy is strongly advised.

More recently, the international community has been looking at the transformative changes needed for the conservation, restoration, and wise use of biodiversity, considering broader social and economic goals in the context of sustainable development. Those changes are defined as being the “*factors in human society at both the individual and collective levels, including behavioural, social, cultural, economic, institutional, technical, and technological dimensions, that may be leveraged to bring about transformative change*”⁹.

Based on the literature review and on the MAELSTROM's first webinar, the working group proposes a list of possible actions to induce transformative changes by relevant ML stakeholders, within the 3 clusters where this study focuses (Tables 8-10): i) Societal behavioural change and citizen science to reduce ML and support circular economy; ii) Research on ML and development of blue technologies for removal prevention and use; iii) International cooperation and capacity building for ML removal, reuse and mitigation actions.

Funders play a key-role on supporting ML innovative research and technology. Priority should be given to capitalize successful legacies while also investing in new

⁹ IPBES work programme 2019-2030 - https://ipbes.net/sites/default/files/decision_ipbes-7_1_en.pdf

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approaches. The proliferation of ML initiatives is often leading to repetitive and ineffective initiatives. On this regard, funders' internal coordination working groups could represent a good solution to deliver programmatic strategical lines and to contribute to map and control ML efforts regionally and where possible, globally. Another priority is the financing of actions leading to the accuracy and standardization of international open-access data sets on ML and the promotion of equal access to funds, especially for Least Developed Countries (LDCs). On this regard, the group suggest funders to organize open workshops and capacity building sessions on how to access and properly use the funds available. Projects aimed at reaching public-friendly scientific contents and awareness activities should be rewarded and promoted, especially when based on "glocal" approaches, as local actions and synergies among communities have proven to be successful on ownership and long-term positive outcomes of the fight against ML.

International and Regional authorities are key actors regarding the adoption and integration of new scientific knowledge and blue technologies into development plans. As authorities oversee the execution of international projects and initiatives, having a "full picture" of what is happening in a certain region, they become crucial actors to map, identify and make gaps, challenges and best practices visible. On this regard, the group proposes the creation of capacity building regional hubs to foster the exchange of cultural and geographically specific issues which might delay or catalyse marine litter solutions. Such hubs would also work as ambassadors for the horizontal (within institutions) and vertical (across institutions and levels) alignment of international, national and local ML frameworks and as ML dissemination and communication drivers. Another priority should be to publicly and practically incentivize the creation of green jobs and environmentally friendly choices across sectors (from industry to citizens) by allocating financial incentives. Finally, to call for citizen-science programs to be implemented in school programs, inspiring young generations to pursue green jobs.

National and Local authorities should focus on incentivizing the transition to low pollution and circular economy processes through the support the development of options for unsustainable products, as e.g. single use plastics, implementation of codes of good practices, compensation mechanisms and the creation of green jobs. Other priorities should include the setup of expert working groups to provide national ML stakeholders and actors the necessary legal and practical guidance on national and international cooperation initiatives and opportunities regarding plastic reduction and plastic management. Another important priority is the need to disseminate clear goals and actions regarding marine litter and plastic pollution, compliant with international frameworks and laws - avoiding overlapping or conflicting information - and fund initiatives accordingly. Citizen related initiatives, such as communication campaigns, clean-ups and tools to ease and enhance citizen's awareness of waste management should also be considered. Nevertheless, the internationalization of successful initiatives such as technologies and networks should be fully supported by national and local authorities.

Companies are the main responsible for the product chain and represent the link between this chain and the consumer. Thus, they should have a double role, both on addressing the product chain through their suppliers, raw materials and

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production methods and towards consumers, by correctly labelling, packaging and informing on market products and services. The replacement of plastic with more environmentally friendly materials and the implementation of resource-efficient processes are fundamental to achieve good environmental standards, including reducing plastic pollution and marine litter. Another key asset is for companies to partner with scientific institutions and other relevant stakeholders, for the development of effective and long-term ML/plastic pollution solutions while also leveraging on company's corporate social responsibility programs to support and fund local, national and international projects and initiatives.

The **scientific community** has a strategic role on creating new scientific knowledge and technological advancements for effective solutions to tackle marine litter. Scientists and research institutes should put efforts into finding, sharing and communicating any new scientific findings to relevant stakeholders and to society. This can be done through open-access events, dedicated workshops and capacity-building actions aimed at creating opportunities between North-North, North-South and South-South researchers and stakeholder institutions. On this regard priority should be given to “brokers”, a new professional which works towards bridging scientific findings and creating dialogs among researchers and stakeholders for an effective comprehension and ownership regarding ML. Researchers should also engage and promote educational and citizen-science programs as a part of their regular research activity and to offer their scientific advice to governments, institutions, private sectors, academia and society, whenever needed.

The **educational sector** represents a crucial platform of knowledge and change: from one side it is responsible to prepare students with the right knowledge and tools to face global challenges, including ML; from another, today's students are the decision makers of the future. In this way, it is imperative to identify the best educational approaches to transmit concepts, challenges, and urgencies; this can be done through hands-on and participative activities based on a combination of disciplines (es. maths, science and arts). Awareness raising events extended to families, alongside the production of informative materials, on-site visits to waste management and/or plastic-related companies and the participation at international contests, all represent good opportunities to understand, reflect and propose solutions to the ML and plastics issue. Academia should integrate citizen-science initiatives as part of regular academic program. Networking actions across and within academic institutions should be widely promoted, alongside the appropriate recognition of positive capacity building and international cooperation initiatives regarding ML within academic settings.

Citizens are essential in adhering to and promoting a blue circular economy paradigm. Through their personal choices, citizens drive and accelerate environmentally friendly policies and practices, for example by improving the plastic collection rates of recycling programs or by advocating for politicians and producers to align with international environmental standards (including ML). Through active participation at awareness raising events such as clean-ups and capacity building and dissemination workshops, citizens can be empowered to become ambassadors of the ML issue and increasingly spreading the word on the urgency and on the correct behaviours, such as a responsible consumption, to

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mitigate it as well as becoming citizen-scientists, engaging in data collection activities for scientific purposes.

7.1. Societal behavioural change and citizen science to reduce ML and support circular/blue economy

Table 8 - Suggested actions for Societal behavioural change and citizen science to reduce ML and support circular/blue economy

Stakeholder	Proposed actions	Description
FUNDERS	Demand public awareness on project proposals	Call for projects to have clear scientific communication and public awareness activities.
	Demand indicators	Require M&E indicators regarding public perception and awareness to be included in funded projects.
	Prioritize "glocal" approaches	Prioritize "glocal" approaches on ML, where synergies among science and communities are established as a way of creating local ownership.
	Promote legacies on societal behaviour practices	Show case positive results to inspire new proposals.
	Simplify and promote fair access to funds	Set workshops and capacity building sessions for smaller enterprises and CSOs working on the ML issue regarding access to funding procedures.
INTERNATIONAL & REGIONAL AUTHORITIES	Incentivize citizen-science in young generations	Incentivize citizen-science programs in school programs from early years as a basis for future green jobs. Promoting international citizen-science exchanges across regions.
	Demand and support accountability and coherence across sectors dealing with the public	Set working and support groups to support diverse stakeholders, including citizens, on their activities regarding ML
	Promote best practices on societal behaviour regarding ML	Use institutional channels to give visibility to virtuous results and environmentally friendly products and choices.
	Provide practical guidance and tools to stakeholders and citizens	Use technology to promote horizontal dialogues among institutional actors, scientific experts, stakeholders, and civil society. Provide practical guidance and tools.
	Inspire	Lead inspirational movements to gather society against common problems through effective strategic programs, communication, and coherence.
NATIONAL & LOCAL AUTHORITIES	Align international, national and local frameworks coherently	Set and disseminate clear goals and actions, compliantly with international frameworks and laws, avoiding overlapping or conflicting information

	Map and support and promote local and national best practices	Support successful initiatives to be expanded and/or replicated in similar contexts
	Promote sustainable and circular economy paradigms across sectors	Provide environmental policies which incentive a transition to low pollution processes across sectors; Promote codes of good practices. Incentivize the creation of green jobs Ease citizen's waste management actions also in natural settings (trails, beaches) where often it is difficult to find appropriate indications.
COMPANIES	Be innovative regarding production chains	Support the replacement of plastic with more environmentally friendly materials. Sustain processes to become resource efficient.
	Provide clear labelling and communication to clients	Provide clients with information regarding the production chain and the environmental impact of the products being produced
	Have a Corporate Social Sustainability Program	Act responsibly by supporting your community wellbeing by investing in ESG actions (environment, social and governance)
	Network	Be part of existing global and national networks committed to tackling marine litter and other environmental issues.
SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY	Improve scientific communication	Improve communication towards the public on scientific findings and technological advancements regarding ML; invest in "brokers" to bridge stakeholders' dialogues
	Engage in educational and citizen-science programs	Engage and promote educational and citizen-science programs as a regular researcher activity
	Network with stakeholders and understand their issues	Participate at networks where the private sector is well represented to better explain and understand stakeholder's issues which might delay the ML resolution
EDUCATIONAL SECTOR	Promote discussion on "global issues" as part of the educational program	Set moments of discussion inviting experts and calling for students and teachers to share their views on workable solutions
	Organize awareness events and produce informative materials using multidisciplinary approaches	Use hands-on and participative activities through multidisciplinary approaches combining science, arts, literature, and movement to organize awareness events and to produce informative materials regarding ML. Invite parents to be an active part of activities.
	Reach to scientific institutions and private sector to create collaboration programmes	Contact scientific institutions and private companies to ask for their support and knowledge to set collaborative programs and actions with students.
CITIZENS	Engage in awareness raising events such as clean-ups and become more informed on different types of plastics and its disposal cycle	Participate at public events, conferences and workshops to be better informed on the state of the art regarding ML, types of plastics and viable alternatives.

Choose compostable alternatives to plastic, reuse and recycle wisely. Re-think consumerism.	Become a responsible consumer by choosing wisely and opt for recycled/recyclable and environmentally friendly goods.
Become a citizen-scientist and help collecting data for scientific purposes	Reach your local scientific community and offer your time to volunteer in citizen-science and awareness raising projects; Spread the word on ML tackling actions available to other citizens across the world; Consider using social media and public events to increase efforts on awareness raising.
Use your voice-advocate, communicate, engage and inspire other to tackle marine litter	Reach your community and use social media to create awareness on ML. Demand local politicians to address marine litter on your city on their mandates. Demand private sector to correctly label products on their origin and disposal management.

7.2 Research on ML and development of blue technologies for ML removal and prevention

Table 9 - Propositional actions to inspire research on ML and development of blue technologies for ML removal and prevention

Stakeholder	Proposed actions	Description
FUNDERS	Support stakeholders' national and international networks	Ensure that national and international key stakeholders have fair access to funding and encourage international consortiums and networks
	Promote and support ML research and mitigation actions	Support national and international scientific and blue technological projects ML related and also designed to develop mitigation actions.
	Support and promote the innovative projects extension	Re-fund and/or capitalize successful legacies from previous projects and actions focused on ML research and mitigation and promote synergies among innovations.
	Encourage the standardization of international datasets on ML and open access data	Promote the fair access to scientific free access data, promoting the projects extension and new scientific knowledge
	Support the exchange of national and international scientists among research institutions	Foster national and international cooperation and exchange of knowledge, technologies and skills.
	International Opportunities	Empower new label and job opportunities and encourage investment in research for new technologies to tackle marine litter

INTERNATIONAL & REGIONAL AUTHORITIES	Promote alignment of international, national and local frameworks	Promote global agreements and the alignment for funding strategies, capitalizing already achieved results from previous projects
	Define target groups	Identify international and regional R&D projects and networks, NGOs and stakeholders.
	Support and promote new knowledge and skills related to ML mitigation solutions	Promote global innovations, new knowledge and technologies, through new research opportunities and initiatives.
	To developing and adopt supervision measures	Oversee the execution of international and global projects and initiatives, encouraging good practices, new ideas and promoting scientific and technological innovation
NATIONAL & LOCAL AUTHORITIES	New Opportunities	Empower new local and job opportunities and encourage investment in research for new technologies to tackle marine litter
	Promote the alignment with international, frameworks	Promote funding strategies in compliance with international and regional frameworks
	Identify local and national ML gaps and priorities to be addressed	Identify local and national gaps and priorities to be addressed, involving multiple stakeholders to propose new solutions.
	Define target groups	Define local and national key target groups to map and capitalize successful networking and R&D initiatives.
	Promote good practices and blue circular economy	Have dedicated working groups to proper support stakeholders' diversity Implement regulations and policies to reduce plastic waste and plastic packaging Encourage research projects for long-lasting solutions to promote circular economy Promotion of the 6Rs: Rethink, Refuse, Reduce, Reuse, Recycle, Repair. Promote long-lasting funding strategies for new recycling process and valorisation of marine litter.
COMPANIES	Support and promote innovation	Entrepreneurs and innovators are well positioned to develop new methods and technologies to deal with marine waste, engaging industry along the entire value chain
	Incentivize multilateralism and strategic partnerships	Promote national and international cooperation, strengthening multilateralism and multi-stakeholder partnerships focused in new technological solutions to tackle ML
	Promote and support blue investment	Promote the investment and/or co-funding in blue technologies for prevention, removal, recycling and valorisation of marine litter

	Funding	Donate and support local, national and international research projects and initiatives
	Networking	Co-development new partnerships with academy and other ML related stakeholders
SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY	Create and share new scientific knowledge	To investigate temporal and spatial distribution of the marine litter, with focus on the accumulation hotspots. To investigate the marine litter impacts on ecosystems and human health. Co-develop blue technologies for ML removal and valorisation
	Promote partnerships with private sector for effective solutions	Develop partnerships with the private sector and other relevant stakeholders for effective ML solutions
	Networking Initiatives	Promote and participate at networks with the private sector and other key stakeholders to understand the main gaps which may delay the ML resolution
	Technology and innovation	Propose and develop innovative research and technologies to tackle marine litter
	Science Dissemination	Organize scientific, training and capacity-building events and participative workshops as a "think thank" to discuss and develop new solutions
	Citizen-Science initiatives	To develop and promote Citizen-Science initiatives new Science and Society projects and initiatives involving multiple society actors
	Communication skills	Uniformize communication through the standardization of methodologies, terminologies, and strategies. Promote positive action-related communication
	EDUCATIONAL SECTOR	Organize awareness events and produce informative materials using multidisciplinary approaches
Promote discussion on multiple global issues, including ML, as part of the educational program		Bring research projects into schools through the organization of interactive classes with scientists. Promote "thinking outside the box," in the search of new solutions. Encourage students to increase knowledge about the environment and its problems. Implement Arts and Science programs
Promote educational and citizen-science initiatives.		Promote educational and citizen-science initiatives as part of regular academic programs
CITIZENS	Mobilize citizen action and help to collect data for	Reach your local scientific community and offer your time an active volunteer in citizen-science projects in collaboration

	scientific purposes	with scientists with the process of knowledge production. Collect data for scientific purposes using protocols and digital applications developed and validated with scientists. Be part of building recognition of the value of citizen science data contributing to the official statistics.
	Science and Society activities	Engage in ML awareness raising initiatives such as clean-ups, conferences and community actions.

7.3 International cooperation and capacity building for ML removal and mitigation actions

Table 10- Propositional actions to inspire international cooperation and capacity building for ML removal and mitigation actions

Stakeholder	Proposed actions	Description
FUNDERS	Support ML international networks	Support the creation of science-driven international ML networks which can gather and coordinate smaller initiatives to avoid dispersion and optimize efforts. Identify focal points to work as a contact point for specific issues.
	Map, gather and capitalize positive outcomes of international innovations and initiatives.	Summarize past ML legacies and avoid repetitive initiatives by setting specific targets, priority areas and needed innovations. Have coordination cabins to assure the correct implementation of initiatives compliantly with international frameworks and ongoing efforts.
	Promote the exchange of international experts among research institutions	Exchange programs among researchers, with a specific focus on sea pollution/marine litter, should be promoted for a continuous scientific international contamination.
	Support the standardization of international datasets on ML and	With the proliferation of ML data and initiatives, efforts to summarize, standardize and provide free access to reliable data should be intensified.

	promote its accuracy and fair and open access	
	Simplify and promote fair access to funds for Least Development Countries (LDCs)	Assure LDCs can access funds for national based marine litter research, technological development and citizen engagement. Create support lines to achieve this aim.
INTERNATIONAL & REGIONAL AUTHORITIES	Promote alignment of international, national and local frameworks	Promote the horizontal (within institutions) and vertical (across institutions and levels) alignment of international, national and local frameworks
	Support and promote innovations, knowledge and skills related to ML mitigation solutions coming from different continents	Promote national innovations and knowledge and empower LDCs based technologies, research and initiatives to be visible and sustainably used.
	Create regional capacity building hubs on ML	Create regional capacity building hubs to facilitate the exchange of cultural and geographically specific characteristics regarding marine litter.
	Support the creation of green jobs	Support the creation of green jobs as part of economic and educational strategic plans.
NATIONAL & LOCAL AUTHORITIES	Align international, national and local frameworks coherently	Set and disseminate clear goals and actions, compliantly with international frameworks and laws, avoiding overlapping or conflicting information
	Support national hubs and incentivize its internationalization	Support the creation and maintenance of national hubs/platforms/networks and incentivize its internationalization (e.g., Plastic Pact)
	Provide legal support, practical guidance, and tools to ML actors	Set expert working/supporting groups to provide national ML actors with legal and practical guidance on national and international cooperation initiatives
	Provide capacity building and participative actions across sectors	Organize workshops and capacity building actions to different stakeholders' groups regarding ML and international cooperation frameworks and opportunities.
	Identify national ML gaps and priorities to be addressed	Identify gaps and priorities to be addressed by international projects and mediate stakeholders' interests for successful outcomes
COMPANIES	Share good company practices and know-how	Openly share good company practices and know-how regarding waste management (such as plastic) within the production chain
	Offer training and capacity building on plastics to staff and suppliers	Offer training to staff and suppliers regarding the company's supply chain relating to plastics and its management
	Donate to international initiatives regarding ML	Leverage on company's corporate social responsibility programs to donate and support local, national and international ML initiatives.

	Partner with scientific institutions and other relevant stakeholders on sea pollution	Partnership with scientific institutions and other relevant stakeholders for the development of effective and long-term ML solutions.
	Create and foster green jobs	Promote green jobs as part of company's profile.
	Network	Participate at existing global and national networks committed to tackling marine litter and other related environmental issues.
SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY	Create new knowledge and capacity building contents on ML	Contribute to the creation of new, relevant and open scientific knowledge and capacity building contents on marine litter
	Offer scientific advice to ML stakeholders	Offer scientific advice to ML stakeholders, ranging from the private sector to national and international authorities at all levels and civil society organizations.
	Partner with the private sector for ML solutions	Partnerships with the private sector and relevant stakeholders for effective ML solutions
	Organize international scientific dissemination events on ML	Organize scientific and capacity building events and opportunities among North-North, North-South and South-South countries.
EDUCATIONAL SECTOR	Promote exchange programs among academic institutions on ML and sea pollution areas	Promote exchange programs among North-North, North-South and South-South educational institutions, specifically regarding ML.
	Promote educational and citizen-science initiatives.	Promote educational and citizen-science initiatives as part of regular academic programs
	Create awards to recognize positive ML academic-related initiatives	Create awards to recognize positive capacity building and international cooperation initiatives regarding ML within academic settings.
	Network with other academic institutions on the fields of ML and Sea Pollution.	Participate in environmental related networks at national and international level
CITIZENS	Engage in ML capacity building and awareness raising initiatives	Engage in ML capacity building and awareness raising initiatives such as clean-ups, conferences and community actions.
	Become a volunteer citizen-scientist and a ML activist.	Become a citizen-scientist (follow international protocols and scientific guidance) and spread the word on ML tackling actions available to other citizens across the world. Complaint on observed irregular behaviours of governments, private sector, services providers and communities.

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		Join a science-based support group to tackle ML.
	Advocate for ML policies and measures, at national and international level.	Use your power to ask for political engagement on ML issues, demanding solutions and preventive actions across sectors, especially for LDCs who often suffer the consequences (waste) of the high plastic consumerism rates of developed countries.

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Annex - Mechanical and chemical technologies developed during the last decade within worldwide and EU projects to tackle marine litter.

- EUROPEAN PROJECTS

marGnet

The marGnet project focuses on marine litter produced by the fishing industry deposited on the seabed. It has developed an innovative prototype to use low-temperature pyrolysis for the synthesis of marine fuels from marine litter, compliant with ISO 8217 DMA and DMB class. The process provides significant fuel samples and therefore is capable of being applied on a larger scale.

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MAELSTROM project leverages on the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal compounded with blue circular economy. Marine litter will be recycled through an additivation with recycled fibbers into high performance composite and through hot pressing of hardly recyclable litter into laminates and panels. All the remaining litter will be transformed by low-temperature pyrolysis into second-generation oils. Moreover, an innovative floating barge will be developed with a cable based underwater robot; the underwater robot uses different tools mounted on its head as a drudge to collect smaller litter and a gripper and hook to grasp larger litter. The project will also see the implementation of a 'Bubble Barrier'(described below), an automated air-bubbles barrier to retrieve floating items.

InNoPlastic

In-No-Plastic project works on the development and application of several nano, micro, and macro-plastic clean-up technologies in aquatic ecosystems. It uses ultrasounds to gather nano and micro-plastics to make it easier to retrieve bigger pieces of plastics from the water. Syngas is produced by a chemical process involving direct and indirect gasification and pyrolysis. It can be used for producing both electrical and thermal energy. A mobile drum screw, constructed to let the fish enter and exit freely and safely, filters the litter and macro-plastics from the water flows. SEEKer robot cleaner is an autonomous vehicle equipped with robotic hands to collect plastic waste from beaches, from a minimum size of a cigarette butt up to 20/30 cm in diameter. It is able to avoid obstacles thanks to ultrasonic distance sensors to reach areas that are difficult to access. It has an autonomous mechanism for emptying the bin, equipped with solar panels and will be operational from 2023.

CLAIM

CLAIM project aims to improve the plastics' prevention and management in-situ through new technologies and methodological approaches for sea monitoring and cleaning actions. Five innovative technologies to monitor and to prevent marine litter entering the sea include: i) a pre-filtering system to sort and collect marine litter; ii) a photocatalytic nanocoating device to degrade microplastics in wastewater treatment plants; iii) a pyrolizer to turn the marine litter collected into

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energy, powering ships and heating up ports; iv) a floating boom to collect litter at the river mouth; v) a FerryBox systems composed by an automated seawater sampling device and a passive flow-through filtering system, to be installed on ships.

GOJELLY

GOJELLY is uses a bio-based technology that comes from nature and is totally sustainable as source of innovative solutions to tackle marine litter issue. The project uses the jellyfish mucus to remove almost the whole amount of nano and micro-plastics present in the wastewater through flocculation. This innovative approach will lead to less presence of plastic in the ocean.

- **COMPANIES**

The Great Bubble Barrier

The 'Bubble Barrier' is an automated air-bubbles barrier to retrieve floating items and debris submerged in the water column in rivers. It can intercept plastic debris from 1 mm up to 1 m. The Great Bubble Barrier company has developed this innovative design that consists of a screen of bubbles, created by placing a tube with holes at the bottom of the waterway connected to a compressor, in combination with a waste collection system. The generated bubbles create an upward current that brings suspended plastic waste to the surface of the water. By placing the Bubble Barrier in a certain angle, the natural current guides the waste to the waterway side, where it is retained in the catchment system. This technology is already installed in Amsterdam's canals and within MAELSTROM project will be set in an estuary area in Portugal.

River Cleaning

'River Cleaning is an intelligent floating modular barrier that does not compromise the navigability of small boats and ships. It is designed to intercept floating waste in streams by its rotation before they reach the sea. River Cleaning works autonomously and it operates both day and night.

EcoCat

EcoCat is a fully electric catamaran developed in collaboration with local waste-management in Veneto Region by OMD. It has a conveyor belt that can collect floating plastic from the water and transport it into a removable bin, that can be unloaded with a mechanism located on the top of the boat. It is designed to be efficient and completely ecological because it is made of linen fibre and it is energetically autonomous thanks to its 5 square meters of solar panels.

The Trash Wheel

Mr. Trash Wheel is a semi-autonomous trash interceptor that is placed at the end of a river, stream or other outfall. The rake lifts litter out of the water and onto his conveyor belt, that moves very slowly but is strong enough to lift any type of waste. When trash reaches the top of the conveyor belt it falls into a dumpster sitting on a separate floating barge.

Everwave

Everwave's mission is to prevent the entrance of marine litter in the oceans using rubbish collection boats. One is called CollectiX15 and is equipped with AI sensors that can smartly analyse the garbage and collect marine litter through a conveyor belt. A drone identifies garbage hotspots to support the boats' activities. The boats have been further developed in such a way that they not only adapt to the general conditions of large rivers, but they are also able to navigate through smaller canals and river branches.

Thomsea

By drawing on the natural power of water, THOMSEA, thanks to its trawls, participates in numerous international projects for maritime and river pollution clean-up to collect marine litter. The trawl net has been constantly improved and the development and use of new tools for collecting and washing algae on beaches has become a second important area of development.

Archimedean Drum Screw

FishFlow Innovations has developed Archimedean Drum Screw¹⁷, an innovative rotary drum screen that effectively separates solid objects from the intake water. It is a mesh screen that is tightly fitted around an Archimedean screw, built with a composite material with a special designed entrance. Its characteristics let fish return unharmed to surface waters and reduce the costs for the processing of solid wastes. As a result, the rotary drum screen is 100% fish-friendly and virtually maintenance free.

Seabin Smart Tech

Seabin Smart Tech is a rubbish bin in the water. The catch bag works as a filter for both macro and micro floating waste and it is made by a 100% recyclable plastic mesh. Seabins are placed in the marinas, ports and yacht clubs, considered perfect places to start helping clean our oceans.